

application of 1 kg CuSO₄ / ha + 0.5% foliar spray 30 and 50 DT. Foliar sprays of CuSO₄ and MnSO₄ 30 and 50 DT were also effective in minimizing BS incidence. Grain yield was not affected by any treatment. □

Status of sheath rot (ShR) in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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We observed ShR symptoms in rice cultivar TN1 in 1966 wet season (WS) at Kalyanpur, Kanpur, UP. As TN1 spread, and later Jaya, ShR became highly noticeable throughout UP. We isolated the causal fungus in 1977, identifying it as *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gams and Hawksworth.

From 1977 to 1987, we surveyed eastern UP, finding ShR in all 5,000 sites visited.

Reaction of scented and export quality rice varieties and cultures to ShR. Faizabad, UP, India, 1980-1981.

Varieties or culture	Disease score ^a
BPMS69, BPMS40 A, Kala Namak, KSR white	1
BPMS1, KSR49-89-10, RP967-11-14-2	2
Basmati 370, HAU11-12, PAU269-1-9-2-1, HPU8106, TR-B-63	3
ADT32	4
BPMS39, Improved Sona, Ratna, SST-2-1909, Type 3, UPR79-1, HAU5-162-3, HAU232-2, Pusa 150	5
AD14185, BK79, BPMS36, BPMS40, BPMS66, Bas 370-A-132-3-9, HAU5-298-2, KSR47-87-1, NM Badshah Pasand, PAU14-2-5-B-5-2-1, PAU29-295-3-3-4-1-1, PAU269-1-9-1-2, PAU269-2-31-1-4, Pusa 150-9-3-1, Pusa 150-9-4-1, Pusa 150-21-1-1, Pusa 167, Badshah Pasand	6
HAU5-30-2, PAU269-1-9-2-4, PAU269-1-9-3, UPR227-9-2-1, UPR227-22-1-1, UPRM 500	7
TN1	9

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

Drought, excess rain, green leafhopper, brown planthopper and stem borer infestations and tungro infections contributed to ShR incidence.

When ShR spread in epidemic proportions in 1980 and 1981 WS, we field-tested 46 scented and export quality rice varieties and cultures for resistance to the disease (see table). BPMS69, BPMS40A, Kala Namak, KSR white (all scored 1), BPMSI, KSR49-89-10, RP967-11-1-4-2 (all scored 2), Basmati 370, HAU11-12,

Rice disease incidence in South Gujarat, India

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Rice in South Gujarat is attacked by a number of diseases every year, that cause considerable losses. We surveyed the occurrence and severity of rice diseases at different crop stages in three districts of South Gujarat during 1983, 1984, and 1985 wet seasons (WSs).

Two to three plots were selected at eight sites and four areas per plot were sampled. Disease intensity was rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* and disease severity categorized as no infection (0), trace (1), moderate (3-5), and severe (7-9).

During 1983 WS, bacterial blight was moderate at all sites except at Nanikarod, where infection was severe in only GR11 and TN1 (check). In 1984, it was severe in GR11, TN1, and IR22 at all sites except Bardoli. In 1985, it was severe at four and moderate at three sites.

Blast was severe in Sathi 34-36 at Navsari in 1983. It was not observed in 1984 but in 1985, it was found in Sathi 34-36 and Mashuri at two sites: Navsari and Vyara.

False smut was found in a moderate form at five sites in 1983; in a moderate form at two sites, and in trace form at one site in 1984; and in moderate to severe form at two sites in 1985.

PAU269-1-9-2-1, HPU8106, TR-B-63 (all scored 3) were resistant.

Carbofuran granules at 1.0 kg ai/ ha at 60 d after transplanting (DT) have economically controlled the disease in cultivar Jaya. Similar results were obtained with 3 sprays of monocrotophos or edifenphos at 0.5 kg ai/ ha, at 15-d intervals, beginning 60 DT. Carbendazim, sprayed as above, controlled the disease but was not economical. □

Kernel smut was observed only at one site, in IR22 in 1983.

Phyllosticta leaf blight in moderate form was observed only in 1983 at Chikhali and Navrasi. Stem rot was found at Navrasi in a severe form only in Entry No. 6869 in 1983 and in Mashuri in 1984.

Udbatta was in moderate form in Halki-Kolam only at Pipalpada in 1983 and 1984. □

A simple method of estimating rice blast (Bl) severity

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Our objective was to develop a simple disease assessment method that can be used by extension workers and farmers. Leaf Bl was assessed in 22 farmers' fields in central Thailand during 1987 dry season. Using a systematic diagonal sampling of 0.16 ha, 10 samples of tillers per field were taken. The top four leaves of each tiller were assessed separately for Bl severity. Average severity for leaves 1 to 4, as well as average severity of all leaves, was calculated for each field. Incidence (infected leaves among the top 4 leaves) was calculated from 400 leaves/field. Average severity (% leaf area damaged) of the top four leaves

and average incidence of infected leaves were calculated for each field.

There is a significant regression function between disease incidence and severity ($R^2=0.954$). The results show that one can estimate leaf BI either by disease severity or by incidence on the top four leaves. Disease severity on leaf 3 is most representative of the average severity of all leaf positions (Table 1, 2).

Assessment of severity on a single leaf is more accurate than that on the whole plant because it is easier to do and saves a lot of time. The close relation between severity in leaf 3 and average severity of all leaves could be used for fungicide testing and crop loss assessment. □

Table 1. Regression models describing the relation between average BI severity and incidence at individual leaf positions. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Average severity	Incidence on leaf 1	$y = 0.333 + 0.118x - 0.007x^2$	0.338
	Incidence on leaf 2	$y = 0.306 + 0.156x - 0.010x^2$	0.560
	Incidence on leaf 3	$y = x/(0.84 + 0.962x)$	0.857
	Incidence on leaf 4	$y = 0.272 + 0.193x - 0.012x^2$	0.657

Table 2. Regression models to predict average BI severity on all 4 leaf positions from an individual leaf position. Bangkok, Thailand, 1987 dry season.

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Regression model	R^2
Severity on leaf 1	Average severity	$y = 1.457 + 1.401x$	0.621
Severity on leaf 2		not significant	—
Severity on leaf 3		$y = 0.012 + 0.719x$	0.916
Severity on leaf 4		$y = 0.480 + 0.637x$	0.913

Orange leaf symptoms on rice

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We tested eight rice varieties for reaction to orange leaf disease. Third- or 4th-instar nymphs of *Recilia dorsalis* free of the orange leaf agent were allowed to feed on source plants 2-3 d. Individual leafhoppers were used for serial daily inoculation feedings on 7- to 10-d-old seedlings in test tubes. Inoculated plants were grown in pots.

Symptoms appeared in IR36, IR50, and FK135 14-20 d after inoculation (DAI). The symptoms included the orange discoloration and inward leaf rolling typical of orange leaf. Infected plants died 35-48 DAI.

Reactions of 8 rice varieties to orange leaf. IRRRI, 1988.

Variety	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (%)	Symptoms ^a
FK135	38	29	Od, Lr,
IR36	38	26	Od, Lr, W1
IR50	40	48	Od, Lr
IR8	39	26	Od, Lr, R1
IR20	35	60	Od, Lr, R1
TN1	40	55	Od, Lr, R1
Reiho	37	38	Yd, Lr, W1
Fukumasari	35	43	Yd, Lr, W1

^a Od = orange discoloration, Lr = leaf rolling, Yd = yellow discoloration with rusty spots, R1 = ragged leaf, W1 = wide angle leaf.

Infected IR8, IR20, and TN1 plants developed deformed leaves with chlorotic and serrated edges and twisted leaf tips 8-12 DAI. These symptoms are similar to those observed in rice plants infected with ragged stunt virus. At 14-20 DAI, the tips of the second and third youngest leaves turned orange. Later, entire leaves became discolored and rolled inward; they eventually wilted. In TN1, about 90% of infected plants developed ragged leaves. Infected plants without ragged leaves died about 7 wk after inoculation, but those with ragged leaves died about 10 wk after.

Plants of japonica varieties Reiho and Fukumasari showed stunting, yellow discoloration, rusty spots on leaves, and wider leaf angle 15-24 DAI. The symptoms are similar to those caused by rice grassy stunt virus. Plants died 26-60 DAI.

IR20, IR50, and TN1 had higher infection than IR8, IR36, and FK135 (see table). None of the plants that showed symptoms after inoculation reacted with antisera to rice ragged stunt, rice grassy stunt, and rice tungro bacilliform and spherical viruses in the latex test or ELISA. □

Rice yield loss to sheath rot (ShR)

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High-yielding rice variety RD23 is severely damaged by ShR (*Sarocladium oryzae* or *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) at heading. We measured yield loss caused by the disease and the effect of fungicides on its control Jun-Dec 1986.

RD23 was transplanted in 4- × 6-m² plots in an incomplete block design with 4 replications of treated-not treated plots

and 2 replications of disease-free plots. The treatment consisted of weekly application of carbendazim.

Linear regression between % ShR disease 1 wk before harvest and % yield loss at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986 wet season.